

Mixed-Ligand Complexes: Part III. Diamine Bis Biguanide Cobalt (III). Acetylacetonate Bis Biguanide Cobalt (III) and 8-Hydroxyquinoline Bis Biguanide Cobalt (III) Salts

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A modified synthesis is described for *cis* diamine bis biguanide Cobalt(III) base and its salts. Absorption spectra of the diamine bis biguanide complexes as also the hydroxo-aquo complexes also reported. The *cis* diamine bis biguanide Cobalt(III) cation has been resolved into optical isomers via the hydroxo-aquo complex in the presence of *d*-tartrate ion. The corresponding *trans* diamine bis biguanide Cobalt(III) also undergoes isomerisation and resolution in the presence of *d*-tartrate ion under the conditions of the experiments.

Acetylacetonate has been shown to react with *cis* diamine bis biguanide Cobalt(III) base liberating ammonia and providing the heterochelate, acetylacetonate bis biguanide Cobalt(III) base. A series of salts have been characterised in the form of red violet crystals. Characterisation has been made on the basis of conductance and equivalent weights. Absorption spectra reveal two ligand field transitions.

Similar reaction with 8-hydroxyquinoline provides brownish red crystalline products of the heterochelate base and their salts. Conductance, equivalent weights and electronic absorption spectra have been examined.

None of the series has yielded to resolution into optical isomers at the Na-D-Line.

Since the description in the literature of the *cis* and *trans* diamine bis biguanide Cobalt(III) complexes little interest has been evinced in these products. For the last four years, there has been going on a considerable activity with these chemical products in our laboratory¹⁻⁴.

We felt that there was a genuine need for a modification of the original procedure for the synthesis of the *cis* complex, which involved air oxidation of a freshly precipitated bis biguanide Cobalt(II) in the presence of concentrated ammonia followed by filtration and neutralisation to provide the sulphate salt. Crystallisation of the sulphate salt often takes several days in a frigidaire. At our hands, the methods appeared tedious as aeration for hours together did not ensure

1. Ray and Ghosh, *this Journal*, 1942, 19, 4.
2. Ray and Majumdar, *ibid.*, 1946, 23, 76.
3. Dutta and Sarkar, *Science & Culture*, 1964, 30, 549.
4. Dutta and Sarkar, Papers in the series "Mixed-Ligand complexes, *this Journal*, under publication.

even 50% oxidation. Besides, the distinction between the two *Cis-trans* isomers was made entirely on the basis of the chemical reactions, namely the formation of an oxalato-oxalate complex, a thiosulphate bridged product and a μ -diol complex¹⁻³.

We thought it worthwhile to undertake resolution experiments in respect of the *Cis* diamine complex, so that some unequivocal proof could be advanced as to the *cis* disposition of the two NH_2 groups. Furthermore, there was felt a necessity of reporting the absorption spectra, too.

Freshly prepared, alkali free bis biguanide Cobalt(II) is readily oxidised in the presence of liquor ammonia by hydrogen peroxide. After filtering off the unoxidised material, together with little Cobaltic oxide, the *cis* diamine bis biguanide base can easily be precipitated out in quite crystalline powder form by the addition of acetone in the cold. Treatment of the complex base with dilute sulphuric acid in the cold provides shining crystals of the sulphate salts. The entire procedure could be completed within three to four hours at the most. Treatment of the diamine bis biguanide Cobalt(III) chloride solution with excess sodium *d*-tartrate provides crystals of the chloride *d*-tartrate salt instead of the pure *d*-tartrate. The red salt was dissolved in minimum water and was allowed to fractionate. Soon there was apparent slow evolution of ammonia and in a few hours the solution was no longer red but a distinct violet. This violet solution deposited crops of crystals, which were distinctly dextrorotatory $[\alpha]_D^{25} = (+) 443^\circ$. On analysis, this turned out to be the hydroxo-aquo bis biguanide Cobalt(III) *d*-tartrate. As the fractionation progressed more and more of the dextro diastereoisomer was recovered. Instead of starting the fractionation of the pure chloride *d*-tartrate we also ran fractionation by the addition of *d*-tartrate to a solution of the diamine bis biguanide chloride. The results were found to be the same. The *cis* complex was also obtained by slight modification of the original procedure (air oxidation, followed by precipitation with acetone etc.) and the chloride-*d*-tartrate fractionated. This was resolved as in the above case, establishing the identity of the two preparations.

In order to verify the *trans* structure of the other diamine bis biguanide complex, the hydroxide sulphate was dissolved in warm ammonia (as recommended)³, treated with barium *d*-tartrate, filtered and the solution fractionated. Once again a violet hydroxo-aquo-complex was obtained, which possessed the same dextro rotation, which might reasonably be ascribed to the complex entity. Thus taking all other chemical evidences (e.g. non-formation of an oxalato-oxalate salt and a thiosulphate to bridged complex in the cold) all that we would like to commit is that the *trans* diamine bis biguanide Cobalt(III) undergoes isomerisation in the presence of *d*-tartrate ion and then shows the same resolution behaviour. Incidentally, this is the first example of resolution of a bis biguanide Cobalt(III) complex, where the octahedral stereochemistry has been satisfied by two other unidentate coordinating groups. We expect to present some more examples of resolution of such complexes containing two biguanide radicals and two other

unidentate groups in some of our forthcoming publications in the series. Unfortunately the sulphate salt of the optically active ion could not be crystallised out, presumably because of the high solubility. However, the racemic sulphate is only sparingly soluble.

We will now describe the absorption spectral studies. Complexes of Cobalt(III) in general show two absorption bands in the visible ranges of the spectra which are added to the two ligand field transitions such as

and $A \xrightarrow{1g} T_{2g}$ Complexes of the type $[Co A_4 B_2]$ are necessarily capable

of exhibiting cis-trans isomerism. When A and B are widely apart in the spectrochemical series, the $A \xrightarrow{1g} T_{1g}$ absorption band is further split giving

rise to three bands in the trans isomer whereas in the cis isomer the splitting is expected to be at best half as much as in the trans. Thus spectra sometimes is a powerful tool for distinguishing cis-trans isomer^{5,6}. Examples where such distinction has been experimentally observed are difluoro bis ethylenediamine Cobalt(III)⁵, $[Co en_2 F_2]^{++}$, chloro-thourea bis ethylenediamine Cobalt(III)

TABLE I

Electronic Absorption Spectral Characteristics.

Complex	Band II			Band I		
	λ (m μ)	ν W. number (cm $^{-1}$)	Molar ϵ (l/mole cm)	ν max. (m μ)	W. number (cm $^{-1}$)	Molar ϵ
1. $Cis[Co(NH_3)_4(BigH)_2](SO_4)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	—	—	—	490– 500	20400– 20000	120
2. $Trans[Co(NH_3)_4(BigH)_2](SO_4)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	—	—	—	485– 505	20600– 19800	80
3. $[Co(OH)(H_2O)(BigH)_2]Tart$	—	—	—	505– 510	19800– 19600	160
4. $[Co(acac)(BigH)_2]Cl_2$	340	29400	1600	500	20000	177
5. $[Co(Oxln)(BigH)_2]Cl_2$	375	26700	3480	480	20800	294
6. $[Co(dipy)(BigH)_2]Cl_2$	330	30303	1145	465– 470	21500– 21300	172
7. $[Co(O-phen)(BigH)_2]Cl_2$	335	30000	1350	470	21300	177
8. $[Co(BigH)_2]Cl_2$	350– 355	28600– 28200	220	475	21100	235

5. Cotton and Wilkinson, Interscience Publishers, 1962, p. 729.

6. Drago, "Physical Methods in Inorganic Chemistry", Reinhold, 1965, p. 176.

$[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}]^{+2}$, bis halogenacetato tetramine Cobalt(III)⁹, bis acetato bis ethylenediamine (Cobalt(III))⁹, to name only a few such examples, where the cis isomers give two bands and the trans provides three bands. It is most often found that the splitting in the cis isomer is so small that a total of three bands is never observed. We have taken the spectral measurements over the range 320 $\text{m}\mu$ to 550 $\text{m}\mu$ for the cis isomers as also the trans diamine bis biguanide complexes. The spectra of the violet hydroxo-aquo complexes have also been recorded. There was definitive existence of only one absorption band in the visible, though however other evidences are available for the cis trans isomerism. Thus we are inclined to comment that the two unidentate ligands being not sufficiently apart from biguanide in their position in the spectro chemical series, visible splitting of the spectral bands is not permitted in the case of the trans species. The cis complex, however, provides a higher molar extinction coefficient.

In addition to the above works, we also describe the syntheses and characterisation of two new heterochelates, acetylacetonate bis biguanide Cobalt(III) and 8-hydroxyquinoline bis biguanide Cobalt(III) complexes.

TABLE II

Determination of conductance in aqueous solution at 36°.

1. $[\text{Co}(\text{acac})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 1.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$					
Dilutions (in litres)	64	128	256	512	1024
Λ^0	114.4	124.3	139.1	148.0	151.2
Λ^∞	134.2	139.51	151.13	157.05	157.74
Λ^∞ (Mean)	= 147.92; Molar conductance = 295.84 mhos. $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$				
2. $[\text{Co}(\text{acac})(\text{BigH})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	: Molar conductance = 293.4 mhos. $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$				
3. $[\text{Co}(\text{oxim})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	: Molar conductance = 344.64 mhos. $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$				

The Λ^∞ values were calculated by Walden formula $\Lambda^\infty = \Lambda^0 (1 + 692 \times n_1 \times n_2 \times v^{-1})$ where Λ^0 = the equivalent conductance at a definite dilution, v = dilution in litres, n_1 & n_2 the valencies of the ions.

A mixed complex with acetylacetonate and ethylenediamine of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{acac})(\text{en})_2]^{+2}$ has long been described and resolved into optical isomers^{10, 11}. This particular study has inspired us to synthesise and characterise a similar complex of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{acac})(\text{BigH})_2]^{+2}$. We have not come across any similar Cobalt(III) complex containing 8-hydroxyquinoline as one of the three bidentates around Cobalt(III).

- Baker and Gaesaar, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, 25, 1161.
- Kuroda and Gentile, *Ibid.*, 1965, 27, 155, 1289; *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1965, 38, 1368.
- Carunchio, Grassini, Strazza and Padiglione, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, 27, 841.
- Werner and Matteson, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1918, 1, 78
- Werner, Schwyzer and Karrer, *Ibid.*, 1921, 4, 115

TABLE III

Determination of equivalent weight.

Complex	Equivalent weight	
	Required	Found
1. [Co(acac)(BigH) ₂]Cl, 1.5 H ₂ O	228	218
2. [Co(acac)(BigH) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ 3H ₂ O	268	261
3. [Co(Oxin)(BigH) ₂]Cl, 2H ₂ O	255	256
4. [Co(Oxin)(BigH) ₂]SO ₄ 4.5 H ₂ O	290	285

Cis diamine bis biguanide Cobalt(III) reacts readily with acetylacetone at room temperature providing violet, silky crystals of acetylacetone bis biguanide Cobalt(III) base. By neutralisation with acids and/or by metathetic reactions a series of salts, have been isolated in pure, crystalline form. These all form red violet crystals and are moderately soluble in water. The chloride provides conductance values which are somewhat higher than the expected values for bi-univalent electrolytes¹². The equivalent weights of the chloride salt and the nitrate salts have been determined by the ion-exchange technique described previously. The experimental values support conductance results. The absorption spectra have been determined within the range 320 m μ to 550 m μ . Two distinct bands are recorded one around 29000 cm⁻¹ and the other at 20000 cm⁻¹ which are typical of Cobalt(III) octahedral complexes¹³. Comparison is made with a number of other bis biguanide complexes, i.e. with the O-phenanthroline, dipyridyl heterochelates as also with the homochelate tris biguanide Cobalt(III). In the acetylacetone heterochelate the bands are shifted to lower energy which is indicative of a weaker ligand field set by acetylacetone. This is in line with the expected positions of the ligands in the spectrochemical series.

Besides the above described salts we also characterised the salt with optically active anions namely, d-tartrate. The camphorsulphonate salt was not quite pure. In pursuance of our resolution studies, the aqueous solution of the above salt was fractionated. Unfortunately the rotations of the different fractions were poor and could not be ascribed to have originated from the complex cation. However, we will like to record here that the only source of light available to us was the Sodium D-line and it is a fact that some complexes might have such optical rotatory dispersion curve that there may be no appreciable rotation at the Na-D-line.

Coming to the other ligand the nature of the reactions was similar. The complex cation 8-hydroxyquinoline bis biguanide Cobalt(III) was obtained in the form of base and a number of other salts. These are all red brown to brown in colour. The variation of the conductance values is in the same range as for

12. Jones, "Elementary Coordination Chemistry", Prentice Hall, 1964, p. 254.

13. Cotton and Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, 1962, p. 572.

the acetylacetonate heterochelates. The equivalent weights of the chloride and the sulphate are close to the expected values. The absorption spectra again reveals two bands around 26000 cm^{-1} and 20000 cm^{-1} . These represent the two ligand field transitions $1\text{g} \rightarrow 1\text{g}$ and $1\text{g} \rightarrow 1\text{g}$. Once again, a comparison

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{A} & \xrightarrow{1\text{g}} & \text{T} \\ & & 1\text{g} \end{array} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{array}{ccc} \text{A} & \xrightarrow{1\text{g}} & \text{T} \\ & & 2\text{g} \end{array}$$

shows that the band is shifted towards lower wave length (higher energy) revealing that 8-hydroxyquinoline provides a ligand field stronger than acetylacetonate.

Attempts to resolve the complex via d-tartrate into the optical isomers have again failed, the different fractions giving no reliable rotation values at the sodium D-line. Here too, we want to impose the same reservation as we had made earlier in this paper in connection with the acetylacetonate heterochelate.

EXPERIMENTAL

Biguanide acid sulphate was prepared following standard procedures¹⁴.

1. *Cis diamine bis biguanide Cobalt(III) base (Crude)*: Biguanide acid sulphate (9 gms. in 150 ml. water) was treated with sodium hydroxide (6 gm. in 50 ml. water) and the solution was added with constant stirring into a solution of Cobalt Chloride hexa hydrate (4.9 gm. in 15 ml. water). There was an immediate precipitation of the yellow bis biguanide Cobalt(II) base along with some green Cobalt Oxide. It was filtered, washed thoroughly with cold water, again triturated with enough water, filtered and washed again. The precipitate was then suspended in liquor ammonia (50 ml.). This mixture was oxidised with a 20 volume Hydrogen peroxide (7 ml. diluted with equal volume of water) at room temperature for 15-20 minutes and then on a steam bath for 5 minutes with constant stirring. The solution was filtered, first at the pump, and then through a quantitative paper under gravity to completely free it from little Cobaltic Oxide and any unconverted bis biguanide.

The solution thus obtained was cooled in ice and the *cis* diamine base was then precipitated by the addition of acetone (250 ml.) with constant stirring. The mixture was cooled thoroughly in ice for an hour and then filtered washed with acetone and dried over KOH. Yield about 4.5 gm. Found: Co, 16.2, N, 47.0%; $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_2)_2(\text{BigH})_2](\text{OH})_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires. Co, 16.3; N, 46.4%.

The base does not seem to be stable in as much as it turns dark on storing in a desiccator. For synthetic uses, the base should be used up as early as possible. The base appears to have some carbonate contamination and the above formula is only tentative.

2. *Cis diamine bis biguanide Cobalt(III) Sulphate*: *Cis* diamine bis biguanide Cobalt(III) base (1 gm.) was suspended in water (5-6 ml.) and was

neutralised with dilute H_2SO_4 in the cold. The solution was filtered and treated with acetone (10-15 ml.) with thorough cooling in ice. The red crystals were filtered and dried in air. [Found: Co, 10.8; N, 31.5; SO_4 , 26.6%; $[Co(NH_3)_2(BigH)_2](SO_4)_{1.5} \cdot 5.5 H_2O$ requires, Co, 11.0; N, 31.3; SO_4 , 26.8%].

3. *Cis diamine bis biguanide Cobalt(III) Chloride D-tartrate*: Cis diamine bis biguanide Cobalt(III) base (1 gm.) was suspended in water (4-5 ml.) and neutralised with dilute HCl to pH 7. The solution was filtered into a concentrated solution of sodium d-tartrate. On cooling thoroughly the cis diamine bis biguanide Cobalt(III) Chloride-d-tartrate precipitated out. It was filtered, washed with ice cold water, then with acetone and air dried. [Found: Co, 10.5; N, 24.9; Cl, 6.0%; $[Co(NH_3)_2(BigH)_2]d-tart \cdot 5H_2O$ requires, Co, 10.4; N, 29.6; Cl, 6.2%].

Fractionation of the diastereoisomer: (A) Cis diamine bis biguanide Cobalt(III) Chloride-d-tartrate (3-5 gm.) was dissolved in a minimum volume of cold water (18 ml.) and allowed to crystallise under a fan. Within half an hour, there was a slow but perceptible evolution of ammonia and the solution turned distinctly violet. The product that began to separate out became oily after one or two crops. The whole amount of the violet solution was allowed to dry up under a fan, taken up with acetone, washed with cold water and again dissolved in a minimum volume of cold water and allowed to crystallise. These fractions were crystalline instead of being oily. All the fractions collected were dextro rotatory and the yield of the dextro form was more than 75% of the starting material. Found for the dextro form: $[\alpha]_D = (+) 443^\circ$ $[M]_D = (+) 2197^\circ$ ($t=22^\circ$). [Found: Co, 11.8; N, 28.6; H_2O , 10.9%; $[Co(OH)(H_2O)(BigH)_2]d-tart \cdot 3H_2O$ requires, Co, 11.9; N, 28.2; H_2O , 10.8%].

Instead of fractionating the pure chloride d-tartrate (after isolation), we also collected crops after leaving a HCl neutralised solution of the diamine Cobalt(III) base in presence of added sodium d-tartrate. This latter procedure appeared to be easier. The fractionations were repeated several times with the same result.

The sulphate salt of the dextro cation could not be separated by trituration with a saturated solution of ammonium sulphate, possibly because of its extreme solubility.

(B) Trans diamine bis biguanide Cobalt(III) hydroxide sulphate was prepared according to the published procedure². The trans diamine hydroxide sulphate was dissolved in a minimum volume of hot ammoniacal water as recommended by the authors, and treated with 1 mole of Barium-d-tartrate and digested on a steam bath with mechanical stirring for half an hour. The $BaSO_4$ was filtered off and the clear solution allowed to crystallise under a fan. This solution also liberated ammonia and turned violet. The crops collected were all dextrorotatory and the yield was above 75%.

Found for the dextro form: $[\alpha]_D = (+) 460^\circ$; $[M]_D = (+) 2281^\circ$ ($t=22^\circ$). {Found: Co, 11.7; H₂O, 10.7%; [Co(OH)(H₂O)(BigH)₂]d-tart 3H₂O requires, Co, 11.9; H₂O, 10.8%}.

Optical rotation measurements were taken in a Carl Zeiss student model Polarimeter with 0.04% solution of the complex.

4. *Acetylacetone bis biguanide Co(III) Sulphate*: The Cis diamine bis biguanide Co(III) base (1 gm.) and acetylacetone (.3 gm.) were suspended in water (about 10 ml.) in a mortar and triturated in the cold. There was a quick evolution of ammonia and silky light violet crystals began to separate. The trituration was continued till all the ammonia was displaced. The product was then neutralised with dil. H₂SO₄ to pH 6.5 and the solution thus obtained was cooled in the refrigerator overnight when violet crystals separated out. These were filtered, washed with alcohol and air dried. Heating on a steam bath was avoided as in that case a very insoluble yellow product separated together with the violet compound, probably a disproportionation product. {Found: Co, 12.4; N, 29.4; SO₄, 20.44; H₂O, (at 120°) 3.5%; [Co(acac)(BigH)₂]SO₄·H₂O requires, Co, 12.47; N, 29.5; SO₄, 20.29; H₂O, 3.8%}.

5. *Acetylacetone bis biguanide Co(III) Chloride*: The cis diamine bis biguanide Co(III) base (1 gm.) and acetylacetone (.3 gm.) were treated as before to expel all ammonia and then neutralised with dil. HCl in the cold to pH 6.5 and the deep violet solution was cooled in a refrigerator overnight and the deep maroon coloured products filtered, washed with alcohol and air dried. {Found: Co, 12.75; N, 30.7; Cl, 15.8; H₂O (at 120°) 6.5%; [Co(acac)(BigH)₂]Cl₂·1.5 H₂O requires, Co, 12.9; N, 30.6; Cl, 15.5; H₂O, 5.9%}.

6. *Acetylacetone bis biguanide Co(III) Bromide*: The chloride solution as obtained above was treated with a concentrated solution of KBr (2.3 ml.) and allowed to cool in the refrigerator. On prolonged cooling for several days some deep violet coloured wooly crystals separated out. These were treated as usual. {Found: N, 25.73; Br, 28.96; H₂O (at 120°) 4.8%; [Co(acac)(BigH)₂]Br₂·1.5 H₂O requires, N, 25.6; Br, 29.3; H₂O, 4.9%}.

The iodide, nitrite and the oxalate salts were prepared by addition of Potassium Iodide, Sodium Nitrite or Ammonium Oxalate to the solution of the chloride salt, obtained in situ, followed by cooling in a refrigerator.

7. *Acetylacetone bis biguanide Co(III) Iodide*: {Found: N, 20.1; I, 37.9; H₂O, (at 120°) 8.3%; [Co(acac)(BigH)₂]I₂·3H₂O requires, N, 20.9; I, 38.1; H₂O, 8.1%}.

8. *Acetylacetone bis biguanide Co(III) Nitrite*: {Found: Co, 12.2; N, 35.7; H₂O, (at 120°) 5.2%; [Co(acac)(BigH)₂](NO₂)₂·1.5 H₂O requires, Co, 12.3; N, 35.1; H₂O, 5.6%}.

9. *Acetylacetonone bis biguanide Co(III) Oxalate* : {Found : Co, 11.8 ; N, 27.5% ; $[\text{Co}(\text{acac})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires, Co, 11.7 ; N, 27.9%}.

10. *Acetylacetonone bis biguanide Co(III) Nitrate* : This was obtained as for the Chloride using dilute nitric acid for neutralisation. {Found : Co, 10.6, N, 30.97 ; H_2O , (at 120°) 9.6% ; $[\text{Co}(\text{acac})(\text{BigH})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires, Co, 10.9 ; N, 31.2 ; H_2O , 10.0%}.

11. *Acetylacetonone bis biguanide Co(III) d-tartrate* : The chloride solution as obtained above was treated with concentrated solution of sodium-d-tartrate (3-4 ml.) with stirring. There was an immediate precipitate of the d-tartrate salt. It was filtered and washed with ice cold water. 5 gm. of the cis diammine bis biguanide Co(III) base was treated such. {Found : Co, 11.0 ; N, 25.2 ; H_2O (at 120°) 10.0% ; $[\text{Co}(\text{acac})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{d-tart} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires, Co, 10.5 ; N, 24.9 ; H_2O , 9.6%}.

It gave an almost zero rotation at the Sodium D-line.

12. *Oxinato bis biguanide Co(III) Sulphate* : The cis diammine bis biguanide Co(III) base (1 gm.) and Oxin (.44 gm.) were mixed together and suspended in water (about 20 ml.). There was an immediate evolution of ammonia in the cold. The mixture was heated on a steam bath to drive out all the ammonia. On heating on a steam bath a dirty yellow product separated out. When all the ammonia was driven out, the product was neutralised with dil. H_2SO_4 in the cold to pH 6.5. The colour of the product turned somewhat red. The product was dissolved in water (about 400 ml.) on a steam bath, filtered and concentrated on a steam bath. On cooling in a refrigerator overnight hard, difficultly soluble red crystals separated out. These were filtered, washed with alcohol and air dried. {Found : Co, 9.8 ; N, 26.2 ; SO_4 , 16.72, H_2O (at 120°) 13.8% ; $[\text{Co}(\text{Oxin})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 4.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires, Co, 10.1 ; N, 26.5 ; SO_4 , 16.5 ; H_2O , 13.9%}.

13. *Oxinato bis biguanide Co(III) Chloride* : This was obtained by adopting a similar procedure as with the sulphate by using dil. HCl instead of dilute H_2SO_4 . {Found : Co, 11.3 ; N, 30.3 ; Cl, 14.2 ; H_2O (at 120°) 7.2% ; $[\text{Co}(\text{Oxin})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires, Co., 11.5 ; N, 30.1 ; Cl, 13.9 ; H_2O , 7.0%}.

14. *Oxinato bis biguanide Co(III) Iodide* : The chloride solution as obtained above was treated with a concentrated solution of KI (3-4 ml) when there was an immediate precipitation of needle shaped crystals. On cooling in a refrigerator overnight it gave hard, very slightly soluble deep red crystals, which were treated as usual. {Found : N, 21.3 ; I, 36.0 ; H_2O (at 120°) 7.3% ; $[\text{Co}(\text{Oxin})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{I}_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires, N, 21.6 ; I, 35.7 ; H_2O , 7.5%}.

15. *Oxinato bis biguanide Co(III) Nitrate* : Obtained as for the Chloride using dilute HNO_3 . {Found : Co, 10.2 ; N, 27.5 ; H_2O (at 120°) 6.5% ; $[\text{Co}(\text{Oxin})(\text{BigH})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires, Co, 10.4 ; N, 27.3 ; H_2O , 6.7%}.

16. *Oxinate bis biguanide Cobalt(III) d-tartrate*: Sodium d-tartrate (.50 gm.) and silver nitrate (.70 gm.) were separately weighed out and dissolved in water (10 ml.) separately. These were mixed together when there was an immediate precipitation of silver d-tartrate. The product was filtered, washed with ice cold water and dissolved in water (about 400 ml.). A solution of Oxinate bis biguanide Co(III) chloride (1.02 gm.) in water (30 ml.) was added to that solution, with stirring, when there was an immediate precipitation of AgCl. The solution was allowed to stand for half an hour and filtered free from AgCl. 5 gm. of oxinato bis biguanide Co(III) Chloride were treated as above taking 1 gm. each time. The solution was then evaporated on a steam bath. As the silver d-tartrate was taken in excess than that required theoretically, to ensure complete replacement of the chloride anion by d-tartrate, the excess Ag-d-tartrate on evaporation of the solution, breaks down and deposits metallic silver. When the volume of the solution was about 100 ml. the solution was filtered from the separated silver and evaporated to dryness, taken up with aqueous alcohol and dried over CaCl_2 . {Found: Co, 9.2; N, 24.9; H_2O , (at 120°) 9.4%; $[\text{Co}(\text{Oxin})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{d-tart}$ 3.5 H_2O requires, Co, 9.6; N, 25.0; H_2O 10.2% }

The product gave a zero rotation at the Sodium D-line.

Fractionation of the diastereoisomers: Both the diastereoisomers viz, Acetylacetone bis biguanide Co(III) d-tart and Oxinato bis biguanide Cobalt(III) d-tartrate were dissolved in cold water at room temperature at 35°C with the help of a magnetic stirrer to give an almost saturated solution and allowed to crystallise under a fan. The first few fractions collected, in both the cases, did not show any significant rotation at the sodium D-line.

All experimental techniques were the same as in earlier studies.

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